

Learning of the Islamic Boarding School Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang

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Abstract: In the world of education, efforts to improve quality should always be carried out, both conventionally and innovatively. To be able to improve the quality of education, it is necessary to improve and improve the teaching and learning process. Likewise with education in pesantren, where pesantren must also always be open to the times, but cannot be separated from its spirit as a pesantren which is a place for regeneration of ulama' which is not identical to the book of turats (yellow book). From various efforts so that students in addition to having to be able to understand the yellow book, are also required to know others. Therefore, one of them can be done by managing the yellow book curriculum based on learning acceleration so that learning objectives are achieved effectively and efficiently. The objectives of this study are: (1) knowing curriculum management, (2) knowing the yellow book reading curriculum based on accelerated learning. This research on curriculum management based on accelerated learning uses a qualitative approach, the subjects in this study are informants, supervisors, and students at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo, Malang. The data collection techniques used are observation, interviews, and documentation. The study yielded findings. *First*, the management of the yellow reading curriculum at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang is effective with indicators, among others, planning carried out by the manager, acceptance of new participants, implementation that runs with maksimal and the output produced is also fairly good. *Second*, the yellow book reading curriculum based on accelerated learning that is carried out is also efficient by looking at the achievements that should be achieved within one year or two semesters, after implementing it only takes one semester, even though students are able to apply the provisions in Nahwu and Shorof.

Keywords: Curriculum, Management, Read The Yellow Book.

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Introduction

Pesantren is education that has been "ingrained" in this country. History records that Islamic boarding schools are the oldest form of indigenous educational institutions in Indonesia whose existence is beyond doubt.¹ Learning in Islamic boarding schools is very identical to the classics or also called the yellow book and the teaching still uses the halaqoh system. Halaqoh in terms of language means "a circle of students or a circle of students, namely several students with a certain number of students form a halaqoh led directly by a kiai or ustadz or also senior students to discuss or study a predetermined problem".²

Learning or reading the yellow book, such as the books of Hadith or the books of Tafsir of the Quran is not an easy thing, it requires perseverance and other sciences such as Arabic, Nahwu,

Shorof, and so on. A person is said to be able to read the yellow book if he is able to apply the provisions in the science of Nahwu and Shorof. Nahwu science is the science that discusses changes in the end of sentences while shorof science is the science that discusses changes in sentence form.³

On the other hand, facing the development of methods applied in educational institutions in general, various traditional pesantren education methods are seen as needing to be perfected. This means that careful research needs to be conducted on the effectiveness, efficiency and relevance of the method to find its weaknesses and advantages. The aspect of weakness is improved and the advantage is maintained. The same call was made by Abdurrahman Wahid which was reiterated by Bruiness⁴

The method applied by pesantren in principle follows the tastes of kyai as outlined in its educational policies. From a

¹ Mr. Tohir Abd. Hamid, *Lora status and scientific competence as the successor of Pesantren leaders*, (new side: LKIS Cipta, 2017), P. 9

² Samsul Nizar., *Social History & Intellectual Dynamics of Islamic Education in the Archipelago* (Jakarta, Kencana Prenada Media group. 2013), hto the. 163.

³ Ali Hasan AlAridl, *History and Methodology of Tafsir*, (Jakarta, PT Raja Grafindo Persada, 1994) cet II thing, 4-5

⁴ Martin Van Bruinessen, *NU Tradition of Power Relations in Search of New Discourse*, tr. LKiS, (Yogyakarta: LKiS, 1994), thing. 185

methodical perspective, pesantren are divided into three groups. The first group is pesantren that only use traditional methods in teaching classical traditional books. The second group is pesantren that use methods adapted to methods developed by formal education. The third group is pesantren which are traditional in nature and make adjustments to the educational methods used in formal educational institutions.⁵

Compared to the first and second groups, the pesantren model in the third group has become a recent trend, including Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang. Darul Khoirot Modern Cottage, Tirtoyudo, Malang Regency is an Islamic boarding school that has lofty ideals, namely printing its students who are proud of Rosulullah Saw. Therefore, the educational institution has a mission in striving for the realization of noble ideals, including producing students who are moral, knowledgeable, able-bodied, preaching to the ummah as well as lifelong service. Nevertheless, Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Kab. Malang always innovates in developing its curriculum in a better direction, because the times demand to always fix what is not good, and make something good to be better. Thus, students will be more useful to the religion of Nusa and the nation.

Therefore. Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang continues to always strive to improve the learning system in the takhossus program. By managing the yellow book reading curriculum based on accelerated learning, so that the students are known (advantages and disadvantages), and can understand the potential of reading books owned by the students, although it will be easy for students in the next stage to develop their potential in terms of kutubiyah. With such a modern pondok darul khoirot education system, the hope of the institution is that the students, can have knowledge in accordance with their respective talents and abilities, and still uphold religious values and moral charity, and especially become a generation that is proud of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). Thus, this Islamic boarding school implements an acceleration program using the prakom method in learning to read the yellow book in its early education. The Prakom method is a practical model of learning the yellow book, its grammar is completed through screening and assessment. However, the Prakom method forms a frame of mind to understand Arabic, in which there is a systematic formula to find out the form or position of certain words.

In Indonesia, acceleration has become a program that has been widely known in the community, even in the world of Islamic boarding schools, the acceleration program has been widely applied, for example, the Darul Dakwah Sukoharjo Islamic Boarding School which implements the Tahfidzul Qur'an acceleration program. Of course, the uniqueness of the implementation of the yellow book reading program as an effort by⁶Darul khoirot modern lodges in responding to changes and demands to maintain the traditional character of pesantren, aroused the curiosity of the author to search. How is curriculum management based on accelerated learning in the modern cottage Darul Khoirot tirtoyudo malang?

Research Methods

This research is a descriptive qualitative research which is a case study somewhere in⁷Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang. The data collection techniques used are: Interviews, observation and documentation. Nevertheless, qualitative research has always been oriented on a phenomenological footing, namely by looking at human behavior what they say and do as a result of how they interpret (understand) their world.⁸

Therefore. In this study, a researcher wants to see the phenomenon that develops as a whole whole, which is not tied to one particular variable or hypothesis. In addition, this approach will make it easier for researchers to find multiple problems, get closer to the subject under study, and be more sensitive and more adaptable to the influence of phenomena in the field. This type of research is field research, which among others has the characteristic that the target of research can be people, events, settings, and documents. Where the target is examined in depth according to the setting and context, with the aim of understanding the various relationships between variables.⁹

Results of Research and Discussion

1. Learning Acceleration-Based Curriculum

Accelerated Learning is a comprehensive system that includes a variety of ingenious ways, tricks and techniques to accelerate and improve the design of the learning process and is also a natural learning process, which is based on the way people learn naturally.¹⁰ From this it can be understood that the purpose of implementing accelerated learning lies in the results. Of course, accelerated learning is different from the creative learning approach that emphasizes more on fun learning with the aim that students feel interested in following learning without paying attention to the results achieved.

However, the purpose of the acceleration program is the achievement of results, the managers of agencies / institutions are required to understand the basic principles that underlie it. These basic principles should be a reference in applying accelerated-based learning. Accelerated-based learning will not work as expected if the program is separated from its ideological foundations. The basic principles of the acceleration program include; Involving all the potential of the mind and body, learning demands student creation, not just the process of knowledge transfer. Learning must be interpreted as a process of creating new meanings involving the brain, nerves and body. Cooperation makes the learning process more on the pattern of interaction between students, Learning takes place at many levels simultaneously, Learning comes from the process of student interaction with reality. Learning must give birth to feelings of pleasure, because negative feelings will hinder the learning process of students. And the Model absorbs the human brain more on images than words.

⁷ Donald Ary, *Introduction to Research in Education, third edition*, (New York: The Dryden Press, 1985), thing 322- 324

⁸ Robert Bogdan dan Steven Taylor, *Fundamentals of Qualitative Research* tr. A. Khozen Afandi, (Surabaya: Usaha Nasional, 1993), thing 44

⁹ Imron Arifin, ed., *Qualitative Research in Social and Religious Sciences* (Malang: Kalimas sahada, 1996), thing 57

¹⁰ Dave Meier, *The Accelerated Learning Handbook: a creative and effective guide to designing education and training programs*, (Bandung: PT. Mizan Pustaka, 2004), p 50

⁵ Mujamil Qomar, *Pesantren from Methodological Transformation to Institutional Democracy*,(Jakarta: Erlangga Publishers, 2006), thing. 150.

⁶ Nur Rahmat, *Study of the Qur'an Tahfidzul Acceleration Program at Darul Dakwah Sukoharjo Islamic Boarding School*, (Thesis of Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta, 2010)

Therefore, teachers are required to make verbal abstractions into concrete images so that they are easier for students to remember.¹¹

In accelerated learning activities, teachers who become program teachers are usually also those who teach in regular programs, it's just that they have been prepared in advance through workshops and workshops so that they have an understanding of educational services for gifted children. Teachers are strived to meet the criteria of good and professional teachers. Broad and appreciative teacher knowledge in teaching should be the standard for teachers whoserve alternative learning. On the other hand, the curriculum between accelerated and regular is not much different. The only difference lies in the arrangement of the program and the shorter allocation of time for the acceleration program. In the first year students will learn all first-grade material in addition to second-grade material. In the second year, they will study the remaining second-grade materials and the entire third-grade materials.¹²

While the accelerated program as a means of special learning services for talented students or students who have extraordinary abilities and intelligence, it requires the availability of a curriculum with special specifications. The curriculum is formatted to serve learning for talented students so that there is a match between the students' ability and the dense and accelerated volume of learning material. Thus, judging from the format, differentiated curriculum has different dimensions as well as aspects of its constituent components. There are several assumptions that are used as a basis for why a special (differentiated) curriculum should be designed for gifted children compiled by several experts. According to Utami Munandar, the differentiated curriculum intended for gifted children includes the concepts and fundamentals of the differentiation curriculum as well as curriculum modifications for gifted children.

Some of the main elements of differentiated curriculum that need to be considered are as follows; Faster material. A more plural understanding of generalizations, principles, theories, and structures of the material field. Work with abstract concepts and thought processes. The level and type of resources used to obtain information and skills. Learning time for routine tasks can be accelerated and time to explore a topic or field can be longer. Creating new information and/or products. Move learning to more challenging areas. Development of personal growth in attitudes, feelings, and appreciation. Bathian in thinking and learning. While the next stage is Curriculum Modification of Gifted Children. In his presentation, Utami Munandar stated that curriculum modifications include; Modification of curriculum materials, learning processes or methods, Learning Products, Choosing the Appropriate Modification, Learning Strategies, and Learning Evaluation and Learning Outcomes Reports¹³

2. Curriculum Management Read the Yellow Book

According to Arikunto and Yuliana (2017: 95) curriculum management is the entire process of joint effort to facilitate the achievement of teaching goals with an emphasis on effort, improving the quality of teaching and learning interactions. Meanwhile, according to Dakir (2004: 3) curriculum management is a curriculum management system that is cooperative,

¹¹ *Ibid.*, thing 54-55.

¹² Reni Akbar-Hawari, *Learning Acceleration Program Implementation Guide*, (Jakarta: Grasindo 2001), thing 122

¹³ Utami Munandar, *Talent Development and Creativity of Gifted Children* (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta 2004), thing 139

comprehensive, and systematic in order to realize the achievement of curriculum goals. Both notions of curriculum objectives, placing learning as part of an inseparable curriculum, are like two sides of a coin, so that curriculum management can be interpreted as an effort to manage learning tools as a reference for learning operations so that they can be carried out effectively and efficiently. These learning tools can be in the form of syllabi, annual programs, semester programs, lesson implementation plans, and so on. Therefore, the curriculum must be managed properly and effectively, ensuring that learning takes place effectively.¹⁴

On the other hand, Triwianto (2015: 25) understands curriculum management regarding how the curriculum is designed, implemented (implemented), and controlled (evaluated and perfected), by whom, when, and in which scope. Management is also concerned with the policy of who is given the duties, authorities, and responsibilities of Java B in order to design, implement, and control the curriculum from which point of assignment, authority, and responsibility in curriculum development. In general, there is a distinction between centralized curriculum development management (centralized curriculum development management or top down curriculum development) and decentralized curriculum development management (bottom up curriculum development).¹⁵

As for reading or reading is seeing and understanding the content of what is written (verbally or only silently). It can also be interpreted as spelling or reciting what is written. Meanwhile, according to Tarigan as quoted in his book, Dalman explained that reading is a process carried out and used¹⁶ by the reader to obtain the message to be conveyed by the author through the medium of written words / language. In this case, reading is an attempt to trace the meaning that exists in writing. On the other hand, Acep Hermawan defines reading as a window of science, classical and modern intellectual treasures and as a means of long life education.¹⁷¹⁸

While the yellow book is the work of previous Islamic scholars written in Arabic without using harakat (bald). Therefore the yellow book is also often referred to as the Gundul book because it is different from the Qur'an which is equipped with harakat (fathah, kasroh, dhomah, breadfruit), although according to munawiroh the yellow book is the Yellow Book is religious books in Arabic, Malay or Javanese or other local languages in Indonesia using Arabic script, which in addition to being written by scholars in the Middle East, also written by Indonesian scholars themselves.¹⁹²⁰

Based on this description, it can be concluded that the management of the yellow book reading curriculum is the process of utilizing all elements of management in all learning activities to take meaning by reciting previous writings, which are printed using yellow paper, using Arabic without harakat, and discussing Islamic science. So that learning can run effectively and efficiently.

¹⁴ Hendro Widodo, et al, *Education Management of Schools, Madrasahs, and Pesantren*. (Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, 2020) P29

¹⁵ *Ibid* P30

¹⁶ Dab Fat Bud, *Great Dictionary Indonesian*, (Jakarta: Balai Pustaka, 1990), thing. 62

¹⁷ Dalman, *Reading Skills*, (Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 2014), thing. P. 7.

¹⁸ Acep Hermawan, *Arabic Learning Methodology*, (Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2011) thing. 217.

¹⁹ Munawiroh, *Teaching the Yellow Book at Pesantren Madarijul Ulum Pelamunan Banten*, *Journal of Education*, (Vol. 10, No. 3, Year 2012), thing. 349

²⁰ *Ibid* P. 350

3. Curriculum Management of Reading the Yellow Book Based on Learning Acceleration at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang

The curriculum management based on accelerated learning at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang includes several steps, including the following; planning, teacher empowerment, student acceptance, implementation of the yellow book reading curriculum based on accelerated learning, and assessment or evaluation.

a. Planning of the yellow book reading acceleration program

Planning ranks first in the management function, because before the activities are carried out careful planning must first be prepared. Planning directs the organization to achieve goals. Planning defines where the advanced organization is in the future and how to achieve it. Planning such as determining future organizational performance goals and establishing as guidelines the resources needed to achieve organizational target tasks. ²¹This phenomenon found by researchers in planning the yellow book reading acceleration program at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang can be seen that the existing planning has gone well. This is proven by the work program that has been prepared by the management of the Education department at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang and is aligned as it should.

EDUCATION DEPARTMENT WORK PROGRAM
MODERN COTTAGE DARUL KHOIROT TIRTOYUDO MALANG
School year 2022-2023

Curriculum Target for reading the yellow book based on learning acceleration:

- 1) Understand nahwu and shorraf
- 2) You can read the yellow book of safinatum najah
- 3) The number of students who passed the program is 100%

No.	PURPOSE	GOAL	ACTIVITIES	SUCCESS INDICATORS	HANDLER / EXECUTOR	DEADLINE	RESOURCES	KET
1.	Improve the yellow book reading acceleration program	Achieved the target of the 2021-2022 curriculum field	Creating a program	The existence of a work program in the field of education	Board of Education	June 2021	COMPUTER	
2.	Develop a training program for yellow book reading instructors	Encourage yellow book reading instructors to develop learning materials through training	Propose workshop/training/training for yellow book reading supervisors	There are teachers who attend workshop/training/training	Board of Education	June 2021		
3.	Recruiting New Students through oral and written tests	Annually class students	Together with the supervisor Carry out the tahsin al-Qur'an and Arabic tests	The number of students accepted according to ability	Board of Education	July 2021	COMPUTER	
4.	Establish Teaching and Learning Process (KBM) activities	Teachers can carry out KBM activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create an effective educational calendar and time analysis • Distribution of teacher teaching hours • Coordinate the creation of KBM devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of an educational calendar and effective time analysis • There is a division of teacher teaching hours • Availability of KBM devices 	Board of Education	July 2021	COMPUTER White board	
5.	Carry out, Yellow Book reading program exams based on accelerated learning	All students take part, Early year exams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate semester exam schedules • Mengkoordinasi the creation of a question script 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is an exam schedule • There is an exam question script • Presence of results (Student Grades) 	Board of Education	From 2021	COMPUTER Paual Exam	

Source: Proker Document of the Head of Education by the Board of Education Darul Khoirot

b. Teacher empowerment acceleration program to read the yellow book

As explained earlier, the readiness of teacher human resources is a determinant of the success of the learning process. The teaching requirements in the accelerated reading of the yellow book program are people who are highly competent in the field of kutubiyah, The perfection of the curriculum concept will not have meaning without being supported by the readiness of teacher human resources as curriculum implementers. Teachers have a central role and determine the success of curriculum implementation Moreover, in accelerated programs, teachers must be able to implement differentiated curriculum, the material qualitatively changes in fattening some essential concepts of the general curriculum in accordance with the guidance of talents, behaviors, skills and knowledge of gifted children. ²²

Therefore, the supervisor who is indeed the stakeholder of the yellow book reading acceleration program in the modern hut Darul Khoirot, is indeed really paid attention to by taking assignment teachers from institutions that do bring an acceleration method so that in the preparation of the syllabus and methods in teaching in accordance with what was previously attended training. On the other hand, the supervising teacher who does teach in the accelerated program does not have a regular jadwa, so that what is the main goal in implementing the yellow book reading acceleration program is achieved. This can be seen by the schedule of teaching and learning activities for the accelerated reading of the yellow book program at the modern cottage Darul Khoirot

²¹ L. Daft Richard, *Management* (Jakarta: Erlangga, 1996), thing 8

²² Conny Semiawan, *Perspectives on Gifted Children's Education* (Jakarta: 1996), thing 119.

KULLIATUL MUALLIMIN AL-ISLAMIAH SUBJECT SCHEDULE
 DARUL KHOIROT MODERN COTTAGE
 School year 2022-2023
 CLASS II

NO	DAY	JAM	MAPLE	GURU	PICKET
01	MONDAY	07.30 -08.30 WIB	BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM	UST UMAR FARUK	Ust abd rohman
		09.30 -10.30 WIB	SULLAMUT TAUFIK	UST ABD SALAM	
		10.30 -11.30 WIB	IPS	UST ACH ROFIKI	
02	TUESDAY	07.30 -08.30 WIB	BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM	UST UMAR FARUK	Ust abd greetings
		09.30 -10.30 WIB	KHOLASOH NURUL YAKIN	UST MISRI YUSUF	
		10.30 -11.30 WIB	REGIONAL LANGUAGES	UST MIIFAHUL KHOIR	
03	WEDNESDAY	07.30 -08.30 WIB	BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM	UST UMAR FARUK	Ust hamim tohari
		09.30 -10.30 WIB	MTK	UST MUAMMAD ARIF	
		10.30 -11.30 WIB	BHS INDO	UST SUYONO	
04	THURSDAY	07.30 -08.30 WIB	BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM	UST UMAR FARUK	Ust faikul mubarak
		09.30 -10.30 WIB	TAKRIR/MUROJA'AH	UST HAMIM TOHARI	
		10.30 -11.30 WIB			
05	SATURDAY	07.30 -08.30 WIB	BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM	UST UMAR FARUK	Ust zaimul fatah
		09.30 -10.30 WIB	PKN	UST AINUL MUKTI	
		10.30 -11.30 WIB	MAHFUDZOT	UST MOH FADLI	
06	SUNDAY	07.30 -08.30 WIB	BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM	UST UMAR FARUK	Ust fadli
		09.30 -10.30 WIB	IPA	UST HAMIM TOHARI	
		10.30 -11.30 WIB	TALIMUL MUTA'ALLIM	UST GRATITUDE	

Source; Acceleration Program Schedule Document by the Board of Education

c. Acceptance of students of the yellow book reading acceleration program

Students who have high intelligence and willingness potential are students who are accepted as participants in the Yellow Book Reading Acceleration program. There are several requirements that must be met by participants of the accelerated reading of the yellow book, among others, passing the Tahsin al-Qur'an and Bahasa Arabic programs and the ability of high student interest. This is done in every semester, when students follow the Qur'anic Tahsin and ArabicAhasa programs.

d. Implementation of the yellow book reading curriculum based on learning acceleration

In the accelerated learning process of reading the yellow book, students build their own knowledge through active involvement in the teaching and learning process. Santri becomes the center of activities, not teachers, so that learning achievements in each month are achieved as they should. As for the achievements in the implementation of the yellow book reading acceleration program, it can be seen from the quality standards of the kining book reading acceleration program as follows

QUALITY STANDARDS FOR THE YELLOW BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM DARULKHOIROT MODERN COTTAGE

NO	LEARNING OUTCOMES	BASIC COMPETENCIES	EVALUATION
01	Santri Must Understand Nahwu Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Kalam, sentence ➤ Mu'rob and Mabni ➤ isim read rofa', nasob, and jar 	Evaluation is carried out every month (summative), end of semester (formative) both orally and in writing
02	Santri must understand the science of shorraf	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It's like a build' ➤ Wazan, sighat (sentence form) ➤ I'lal, and Faidah Wazan 	
03	Santri must be able to read the yellow book of SafinaTun Najah	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Interpreting the Gandul Book of Safinatun Najah ➤ Understanding the position of Yang in the Book of Safinatun Najah 	

By looking at the table, it can be understood that, the curriculum compiled is indeed used for accelerated programs. This can be known from the learning achievements and existing basic competencies that should be achieved within one year or two semesters, only achieved with one semester, of course with the preparation of different curricula and time allocations. On the other hand, to be more effective in the program so that it produces optimal results, it does require students who have intelligence and talent and are fluent in language, have high curiosity, able to learn / work independently, tenacious, face difficulties, have clear goals in every activity, are careful and thorough, have problem-solving skills, have broad interests, and have high imagination.²³

In delivering the material, the approach chosen is the watonan or bandongan method, where the students must have a prakom book and listen to what has been explained by their supervisor related to the material at that time. After the teacher delivers the lesson material, the

²³ Wiharjo, *PLB Directorate Policy in School Development* (Jakarta:2002), thing 10

supervisor must leave time for the content of the question and answer, so that the level of understanding of the students is not only some who understand. On the other hand, this question and answer adds to the dexterity of the students in remembering.

Then in order to be more convincing than the level of understanding of students, it is necessary to deposit material. In this case, students are required to memorize what has been learned before and then deposited to the supervisor one by one. And to ease the burden on the students and so that in participating in this book reading program is not saturated because there is too much material that must be memorized, a *takrir* or *murojaah* together is held, in which all participants read together repeatedly so that from frequent repeated without feeling easy to memorize.

On the other hand, learning media as a support for learning activities for the accelerated reading of the yellow book program is quite adequate and relevant to the needs of students. Learning media includes, among others: White board, LCD projector and material book.

e. Assessment/evaluation

In his presentation, Fitri Nur Rohman said, evaluation activities need to be carried out in several stages, namely measuring first, then assessing or interpreting the measurement results and drawing conclusions from both processes. Thus, the evaluation must be carried out in a process that is not only one-way but needs to go through stages or procedures that are arranged in such a way in detail, while the supervision of the implementation of the yellow book reading acceleration program at ²⁴Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot, Tirtoyudo, Malang has indeed been implemented and runs well in accordance with data exposure. And the supervision carried out by the head of Education at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang went very well. The invigilator not only comes when the students face the exam but the invigilator attends each week according to the predetermined schedule.

While the evaluation of the implementation of the yellow book reading acceleration program at Pondok Modern Darul Khoirot Tirtoyudo Malang has indeed been carried out and is running well, namely monthly evaluations and the end of the program is carried out, both in the form of written and oral evaluations, this can be seen from the existence of document value during students participating in the yellow book reading acceleration program in the modern hut Darul Khoirot tirtoyudo malang, as follows;

EVALUATION RESULTS OF THE YELLOW BOOK READING ACCELERATION PROGRAM DARUL KHOIROT MODERN COTTAGE

NO	NAME	BLN 1	BLN 2	BLN 3	SEMESTER		ABILITY	KET
					ORAL	WRITE		
01	M. Aliman Zaky	80	75	60	70	70	B	Good
02	M. Atar Hafidz f	70	85	65	70	70	B	Good
03	Bayu Indra P	70	70	60	85	80	A	That's very nice
04	Angga Pratama	70	65	60	70	70	B	Good
05	Deni Saputra	65	70	70	80	80	A	That's very nice
06	Rev. ZR	70	80	90	85	80	B	Good
07	Sahrul Fauzi	80	90	60	95	95	A	That's very nice
08	Taufik Hidayat	60	80	60	85	80	B	Good
09	Ifan Ribowo	70	90	55	50	60	B	Good
10	Agil Ramadhani	70	70	65	85	90	A	That's very nice
11	Yuan Ramadhani	75	80	65	60	65	C	Enough

²⁴ Fitri Nur Rohmah, "The urgency of evaluation for education", *Fikrotuna; Journal of Islamic Education and Management*, Vol. 05, No. 01 (Institute for Research and Community Service, July 2017), thing 8

From the results of the evaluation, it can be seen that, in order for what is planned to be achieved and in accordance with what is expected, namely students can read the yellow book quickly and precisely and become a consideration for the effectiveness and efficiency of a learning on the next curriculum, then an evaluation is applied with three types, namely: the ability to be carried out every face-to-face, Monthly evaluations carried out every learning achievement are completed, and semesters are carried out after the accelerated program reads the yellow book ends. However, there are those whose form of evaluation is written and some use oral

Conclusion

Based on the discussion of the findings of the research conducted, entitled "Management of the Yellow Book Reading Curriculum at Darul Khoirot Modern Pondok Tirtoyudo Malang", researchers can conclude that the *first* Curriculum Management of Reading the Yellow Book at Darul Khoirot Modern Pondok Tirtoyudo Malang begins with the planning of the yellow book reading curriculum Held every time before the new school year. The planning includes improving acceleration programs, empowering teachers, accepting new students, curriculum implementation, and evaluation or assessment. *Second*, empowering supervisory teachers by taking assignment teachers from institutions that do bring an accelerated method so that in the preparation of syllabus and methods in teaching in accordance with what was previously attended training. *Third*, Acceptance of new students by strictly selecting prospective members of the yellow book reading acceleration program with the ability of Tahsin al-Quran and Arabic through tests both orally and in writing.

The implementation of the yellow book reading curriculum based on accelerated learning includes the preparation of a differentiated curriculum, which is a curriculum that is indeed used in the acceleration program but does not reduce the substance of the curriculum used in the regular program, because the allocation of time and the preparation of subjects are adjusted. And on the other hand, the ability of students and guidance teachers who are really competent and graduated from various screenings. While the last is assessment or evaluation. In this case, the supervisor does not only come when the students face the exam but the supervisor is present every week according to the schedule that has been determined, this is the duty and responsibility of the head of pesantren education. On the other hand, monthly evaluations and the end of the yellow book reading acceleration program for students are carried out, both in the form of written and oral evaluations. All of that is done as a benchmark for the ability of students to undergo teaching and learning activities, as well as a guideline for the ongoing acceleration program to read the yellow book so that it becomes an effective and efficient learning. in the modern hut Darul Khoirot tirtoyudo malang

Bibliography

1. Akbar, R. H. (2001) *Guidelines for Implementing Learning Acceleration Program*, Jakarta: Grasindo

2. Arifin, I. ed., (1996) *Qualitative Research in Social and Religious Sciences* Malang: Kalimasahada,
3. Ary, D. (1985) *Introduction to Research in Education, third edition*, New York: The Dryden Press
4. Bogdan, R. and Steven, T. (1993). *Fundamentals of Qualitative Research* terj. A. Khozen Afandi, Surabaya: National Business,
5. Dep Dik Bud, (1990) *Big Dictionary Indonesian*, Jakarta: Balai Pustaka
6. Daft, L. Richard, (1996) *Jakarta Management*: Erlangga,
7. Dalman, (2014) *Reading Skills*, Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada,
8. Van, M. B. (1994) *NU Traditions of Power Relations in Search of New Discourses*, tr. LKiS, Yogyakarta: LKiS
9. Hermawan, A. (2011) *Arabic Language Learning Methodology*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya,
10. Hasan, A. A., (1994) cet II *History and Methodology of Tafsir*, Jakarta, PT Raja Grafindo Persada,
11. Munawiroh, M. (2012). Pengajaran Kitab Kuning Di Pesantren Madarijul Ulum Pelamunan Banten. *Edukasi*, 10(3), 294574.
12. Munandar U., (2004) *Talent Development and Creativity of Talented Children* Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta
13. Meier, D., (2004) *The Accelerated Learning Handbook: a creative and effective guide to designing education and training programs*, Bandung: PT. Mizan Library
14. Nizar, S. (2013). Social History & Intellectual Dynamics of Islamic Education in Indonesia. *Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group*.
15. Nur, F. R., (2017) "The Urgency of Evaluation for Education", *Fikrotuna; Journal of Islamic Education and Management*, Vol. 05, No. 01
16. Qomar, M., (2006) *Pesantren from Methodological Transformation to Institutional Democracy*, Jakarta: Erlangga Publisher
17. Rahmat, N., (2010) *Study on the Qur'an Tahfidzul Acceleration Program at Darul Dakwah Sukoharjo Islamic Boarding School*, Thesis of Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta,
18. Semiawan, C., (1996) *Perspectives on Education of Jakarta's Gifted Children*
19. Tohir, M., Abd. H., (2017) *lora status and scientific competence as the successor of pesantren leaders*, Selakan baru: LKIS Cipta,
20. Widodo, H., (2020) et al, education management of schools, madrasahs, and pesantren. Bandung; PT. Juvenile Rosdakarya,
21. Wiharjo, (2002), *Policy of PLB Directorate in Jakarta School Development*